

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VIII, August 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

 @pinagpalapublishing

 pinagpala_publishing

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com

“The Significance of Contextualization in the Teaching of Araling Panlipunan”

Chiene T. Guibong

Master Teacher I

Bartolome Sangalang National High School

Division of Nueva Ecija, Nueva Ecija, Region III, Philippines

Teaching always takes place more effectively over empirical instances. This further explains that when there is an actual immersion during the process, the more meaningful learning is. Learning happens much well in an environment where there is localization. Through this specific way, one can have a more thorough understanding of what is being taught or imparted. Proximity should never be a problem as long as the teacher is creative and resourceful enough in making adjustments to make the actual venue of learning suited or corresponding to what is being taught.

If there is really no connectivity of what is being taught to what is really prevalent, then the teacher can find ways on how to have real life applications for such. “The Victory of Lapu-Lapu over Magellan along the coastal premise of Mactan” can be depicted in a landlocked locality by means of presenting the victorious scenario by means of a tableau, a walking diorama or even a travelogue. Such strategies engage the students of putting themselves to the period of history which the event has happened. This enables students to experience how was it to be there in doing the process without bringing an entire class to the nearest coastal premise to make them “feel” the event. This is one sample of contextualization.

Why is it important to contextualize? It is indeed very essential to contextualize because learners can better assimilate knowledge if they can actually relate to what they are learning. They need to experience what they are being taught. Contextualization might help to amplify Filipino culture. The creative juice of a learner's vibrant and inventive cognitive faculties may be likened to the usage of instructional resources in contextualizing. Young generations, who will carry the torch of freedom and unrivaled Filipino idealism, need to be taught these principles, which are beautifully and richly embedded in the backdrop of moral wisdom and amazingly astounding Filipino values. Therefore contextualized teaching is synonymous with empirical or experiential learning. Learning also becomes strong and lasting when exemplifications are part of the learners' daily ways of living. Contextualization therefore makes learning easier to absorb and retain.

How can a teacher best contextualize? Contextualization could be best done by a teacher through intensive and in-depth walk-through with what he/she is about to teach his / her students. Having this so called “walk-through” will not only mean a rigorous preparation and a rich prior knowledge but also a realization of what is to be taught. Realizing what are to be taught will certainly demand time and dedication for the teacher has to consume both time and effort getting through the so named “walk-through” process.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.175-176 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

“Araling Panlipunan” as a subject needs not be a boring and tedious one. It should even be considered as an exciting and fulfilling subject because it provides an empirical re-enactment of the past with the utilization of today’s possibilities and essentials for a productive and beneficial tomorrow.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13346286

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.